

A methodology for identifying core sources and core publications in OpenAlex

[Nees Jan van Eck](#) and [Ludo Waltman](#)

Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), [Leiden University](#), The Netherlands

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1. Introduction

In 2013, CWTS introduced a methodology for identifying so-called core sources and core publications in Web of Science (Waltman and Van Eck, 2013a, 2013b). Core sources are international scientific journals and other scientific outlets in fields that are suitable for citation analysis. Core publications are publications in these core sources. CWTS has used its methodology for identifying core sources and core publications in Web of Science in various applications, most notably in the selection of publications included in the CWTS Leiden Ranking.

OpenAlex is a new bibliographic database that was established in 2022. In many ways it resembles Web of Science, but it has the key benefit that the data is fully open. OpenAlex data can be freely used and distributed without any restrictions. In this report we present a methodology for identifying core sources and core publications in OpenAlex. This methodology is similar to the methodology developed by CWTS for identifying core sources and core publications in Web of Science, but a few adjustments were made to handle differences between OpenAlex data and Web of Science data. We also present the results obtained using our methodology for OpenAlex, including a comparison with the results obtained using our methodology for Web of Science. Our methodology for OpenAlex has already been used in the recently launched Open Edition of the CWTS Leiden Ranking.

We note that several limitations of OpenAlex data were identified during the development of our methodology for identifying core sources and core publications in OpenAlex. These

limitations were discussed with the OpenAlex team. As a result the OpenAlex team made several important improvements to their data.

This is the third version of this report. The first version was published in April 2024 was based on the November 2023 of OpenAlex. The second version, published in October 2024, used the August 2024 snapshot. In the current version of this report, we present results based on the August 2025 snapshot of OpenAlex.

2. Methodology

Our methodology for identifying core sources and core publications in OpenAlex is similar to the methodology developed by CWTS for identifying core sources and core publications in Web of Science (Waltman and Van Eck, 2013a, 2013b). There are a few differences, which relate to differences between OpenAlex and Web of Science in the completeness of the metadata of publications and in the level of granularity of the document type classification. In OpenAlex certain metadata elements are missing for some publications and the document type classification is less granular than in Web of Science.

Our methodology for identifying core sources and core publications in OpenAlex consists of seven steps. We start with all works (i.e., publications) in OpenAlex. In the first five steps in our methodology, we then exclude works based on several criteria:

- Step 1. Exclude works that do not have an *article/review* work type and *journal* source type, or an *article/book chapter/review* work type and a *book series* source type
- Step 2. Exclude works that are not in English
- Step 3. Exclude works that do not have any authors
- Step 4. Exclude works that do not have any affiliations
- Step 5. Exclude works that do not have any references

Steps 4 and 5 deal with works for which affiliation metadata or reference metadata is missing. Missing metadata elements are a limitation of OpenAlex data. Steps 4 and 5 are therefore specific to our methodology for OpenAlex. Our methodology for Web of Science does not include these steps.

In the last two steps, we exclude certain sources (i.e., journals and other outlets):

- Step 6. Exclude sources that do not have a sufficiently international focus (to filter out national journals)

Step 7. Exclude sources that do not have a sufficiently large proportion of works with active references (to filter out trade magazines, business magazines, and popular scientific magazines)

If a source is excluded, all works published in that source are excluded. The sources remaining after step 7 are referred to as core sources. The works remaining after step 7 are referred to as core publications.

In step 6, we determine for each source its international focus. This is done by looking at the countries with which authors that publish in a source or that cite a source are affiliated. More specifically, we calculate for each source a metric called the Kullback-Leibler divergence. The Kullback-Leibler divergence d_i of source i equals

$$d_i = \sum_j p_{ij} \ln \frac{p_{ij}}{q_j},$$

where p_{ij} denotes the weight of country j in source i 's distribution over countries (based on the countries of authors publishing in or citing source i) and q_j denotes the weight of country j in the overall distribution over countries. The lower the value of d_i , the stronger the international focus of source i .

In step 7, we exclude all sources for which fewer than 40% of the works have active references. An active reference is defined as a reference to a non-excluded work published no more than four years before the citing work.

The source code of our methodology is available in [this GitHub repository](#).

3. Results

We applied our methodology to the August 2025 snapshot of OpenAlex. We considered all works published in 2000 or more recently. The total number of works is 202,439,569. These works were published in 223,680 sources.

Figure 1 shows the number of remaining works after each of the seven steps in our methodology.

Figure 1. Number of remaining works after each step in our methodology.

Figure 2 shows the number of remaining sources after each step in our methodology. Some sources include only a very small number of works. Figures 3 and 4 therefore show the number of sources after each step in our methodology that include at least 10 or 50 remaining works.

Figure 2. Number of remaining sources after each step in our methodology.

Figure 3. Number of sources after each step in our methodology considering only sources that include at least 10 remaining works.

Figure 4. Number of sources after each step in our methodology considering only sources that include at least 50 remaining works.

In step 6 in our methodology, the threshold used to determine which sources are excluded and which ones are included is set to

$$d_i = \log \left(\frac{1}{\max_j(q_i)} \right) = 1.5929$$

Using this threshold, 64,354 sources are excluded, while 44,882 sources remain. This is also shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Distribution of d_i for 109,236 sources. The 64,354 sources for which $d_i > 1.5929$ are excluded.

Some random examples of sources that are excluded in step 6 are:

- E-Jurnal Akuntansi (2302-8556)
- Journal of Contemporary Physics (Armenian Academy of Sciences) (1068-3372)
- Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences (2790-9344)
- Iraqi Journal of Science (0067-2904)
- Science and Transport Progress. Bulletin of Dnipropetrovsk National University of Railway Transport (2307-3489)

As these examples show, sources excluded in step 6 have a national or regional focus.

Some random examples of sources that are excluded in step 7 are:

- Political Theology (1462-317X)
- Literature Compass (1741-4113)
- Popular Music (0261-1430)
- Humanities (2076-0787)
- Victorian Literature and Culture (1060-1503)

As these examples show, sources excluded in step 7 tend to have a humanities focus.

At the end of the process, the number of remaining works is 43,708,641. The number of remaining sources is 38,790. These works and sources are regarded as core publications and core sources, respectively. Some core sources include only a very limited number of core publications. There are 35,935 core sources that include at least 10 core publications and 28,911 core sources that include at least 50 core publications.

The results at the level of sources and individual publications are available in an open data set (Van Eck, 2025). More detailed results at the level of sources can be found in the [supplementary material](#). This also includes results based on Web of Science (see Section 4) as well as the results of a comparison to five well-known lists of sources (see Section 5).

4. Comparison to results based on Web of Science

The methodology introduced in this report for identifying core sources and core publications in OpenAlex is similar to the methodology developed by CWTS for identifying core sources and core publications in Web of Science. To what extent do the methodologies for OpenAlex and Web of Science produce identical results? To answer this question, we consider the set of all 9,691,824 publications in the period 2020-2023 that are indexed in both OpenAlex and Web of Science and that can be matched based on their DOI. For this set of publications, we analyze the extent to which the methodologies for OpenAlex and Web of Science identify the same core publications. Three citation indexes were considered in the case of Web of Science: the Science Citation Index, the Social Sciences Citation Index, and the Arts & Humanities Citation Index.

Figure 6 shows the overlap of core publications in OpenAlex and Web of Science. As can be seen in Table 1, 94.5% of the publications are classified in the same way (either as core publication or as non-core publication) in OpenAlex and Web of Science. For the remaining publications, the classifications in the two databases do not agree. In about half of the cases a publication is classified as core publication in OpenAlex and as non-core publication in Web of Science, while the opposite outcome is obtained in the other half of the cases.

Figure 6. Overlap of core publications in OpenAlex and Web of Science.

Table 1. Comparison between classification of publications in OpenAlex and Web of Science as core publication or non-core publication.

		Web of Science	
		Core publication	Non-core publication
OpenAlex	Core publication	8,073,988	305,201
	Non-core publication	231,656	1,080,979

Disagreements between OpenAlex and Web of Science in the classification of publications occur for a variety of reasons. An important reason why some publications are classified as non-core publication in OpenAlex while they are classified as core publication in Web of Science is that certain metadata elements are missing for some publications in OpenAlex. As a consequence, our methodology for OpenAlex may exclude these publications (see steps 3, 4, and 5 in Section 2). Conversely, an important reason why some publications are classified as core publication in OpenAlex while they are classified as non-core publication in Web of Science is that our methodology for Web of Science excludes publications that do not have an 'article' or 'review' document type in Web of Science. The document type classification in

OpenAlex is less fine-grained, and our methodology for OpenAlex is therefore less restrictive (see step 1 in Section 2).

5. Comparison to other source lists

Finally, we compare the core sources identified in OpenAlex to the sources included in the following five lists:

- Bibliometric Research Indicator (BFI)¹: This list was operated by the Ministry of Higher Education and Science in Denmark. It includes the sources used in the Danish Research Assessment, which was discontinued in 2022.
- Excellence in Research for Australia (ERA)²: This list includes the sources that were eligible for institutions' ERA 2023 submissions – that is, scholarly peer-reviewed journals that publish original research and that were active in the period 2016-2021.
- Publication Forum (JUFO)³: This list is operated by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies to support the quality assessment of Finnish research outcomes.
- Norwegian Register for Scientific Journals, Series and Publishers⁴: This list is operated jointly by the National Board of Scholarly Publishing and the Norwegian Directorate for Higher Education and Skills on behalf of the Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research.
- Scopus⁵: This list includes all sources indexed in Scopus.

We matched sources in OpenAlex to sources in the above five lists based on ISSNs. It is important to be aware that this matching approach has significant limitations due to missing and incorrect ISSNs.

For each of the above five lists, Table 2 shows the number of sources in the list, the number of sources with an ISSN, the number of sources with a matching source in OpenAlex, and the number of sources classified as core source in OpenAlex. As can be seen in the table, a substantial number of sources included in the various lists are indexed in OpenAlex but are not classified as core source. Most of these sources were excluded in step 6 in our methodology for identifying core sources and core publications, which means that these

¹ <https://ufm.dk/en/research-and-innovation/statistics-and-analyses/bibliometric-research-indicator/bfi-lists>

² <https://www.arc.gov.au/evaluating-research/excellence-research-australia/era-2023>

³ <https://julkaisuforum.fi/en/evaluations>

⁴ <https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringsskanaler/Om>

⁵ <https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/content#4-titles-on-scopus>

sources do not have an international focus. There are also many sources that were excluded in step 5 or step 7 in our methodology. Publications in these sources do not have references at all or many publications in these sources do not have active references.

Table 2. Comparison of five lists of sources to the core sources identified in OpenAlex.

	BFI	ERA	JUFO	Norwegian Register	Scopus
# sources	21,059	26,241	36,245	38,179	45,755
# sources with ISSN	17,257	26,099	31,524	37,961	44,891
# sources in OpenAlex	15,556	23,950	26,385	30,139	35,323
# core sources in OpenAlex	11,969	18,016	18,890	21,166	23,445

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